

PROSPECTS FOR USING NO-CODE PLATFORMS IN EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION

This article provides general information about the no-code platform and comments on the prospects of using it in the educational process.

Key words: no-code, platform, code writing process, automation, program, site, educational system, educational process.

Introduction

No-code platforms have ideal features for people who have lost their desire to write code. These platforms serve well, in education, in entrepreneurship and even for employees.

With these platforms, humans will be able to create applications, sites, mobile applications and other automated projects for users, as well as automate and maintain many business processes.

No-code platforms in education will be useful in such matters as: creating classes and manuals: No-code platforms, helping to automate teaching materials and manuals for teachers. With such platforms, teachers prepare interactive lessons, curricula, and other materials for students.

Creating reports and students with the help of training: on no-code platforms, it will be easy to create guides and reports for events. With these platforms, teachers can monitor student achievement and development, create student-supervised programs, and interact with students.

Creating discussion forums: on no-code platforms, it will be easy to create discussion forums and redevelop it. These discussions are a good place to make connections between students and exchange their feedback.

Creating surveys and questionnaires: allows you to create no-code platforms, questionnaires and questionnaires. Through this method, teachers, students, and other relatives learn about students, their services, and skills, and make decisions to increase accessibility to them. No-code platforms, going one step ahead in education and using this method, help to expand interaction between teachers and students. Learning this method will also be useful for students, because it is their interest and essence

No-code platforms have several advantages in education. This makes it easier to create platforms, automated applications for events, mobile

applications and other projects. The following advantages help to use no-code platforms in education:

Learning to write code is not required: no-code platforms do not include requirements related to writing code. This allows individuals to be able to create new projects without having to spend a lot of time learning to code. **Development speed:** No-code platforms increase the speed of project automation, and this reduces development times. This facilitates the automation of activities and training sessions, the development of activities and essence.

Job automation: no-code platforms allow you to automate projects, making work easier for employees and students. It will be easy to create services and other guides with customers. **Management and control:** no-code platforms, facilitate project management and control. This helps to monitor student achievement for teachers, monitor employee work processes, and develop the essence.

External shows: No-code platforms, events are associated with external shows, with which applications and applications, sites and other projects can be easily created using these platforms.

No-code platforms will be useful for any stage of training. These platforms serve well for students, teachers and staff and make their work easier. In addition, these platforms help to create teaching materials and facilitate their dissemination. Despite the fact that No-code platforms provide several useful features in education, they also have disadvantages. The following disadvantages may be present:

Application multiples: No-code platforms are created to facilitate the learning process in education, but their instructions and functions take a long time to be understandable. Learning to explore and use these platforms can also cause difficulties for students and teachers.

Clear and limit educational materials: no-code platforms may have limit functions to limit existing educational materials. These limits can create limitations on students ' correct analysis of the learning process.

Good demand of guidance and support materials for teachers and students: No-code platforms are designed to help students in their learning process and provide facilities. It is very important to pay attention to the clear and good application of existing educational materials on these platforms, the presence of specific support materials for teachers and students.

Complex skills and intellectual ability requirements to create custom programs: despite the fact that no-code platforms make it easier to create

programs, but more complex skills and intellectual abilities can be required to create custom programs. This disadvantage can make it difficult for students and faculty to create high-level programs.

Finding reliable and secure platforms: on No-code platforms, making the product safe and ensuring that the data is written requires a lot of attention. Finding reliable and secure platforms is important for students and faculty. For a large number of students, it is important that no-code platforms, despite their shortcomings, but well require the creation of complex programs and provide special support materials. No-code platforms are useful tools to facilitate the learning process in education. These platforms allow students and teachers to facilitate the study of programs of different types to support earlier learning. These programs help students learn a specific profession, which helps them get a quality job.

With the help of learning with No-code platforms, students can learn complex programs while facing challenges. These platforms help students demonstrate their abilities in the educational process and expand their abilities to them.

Also, no-code platforms allow you to increase the amount of free time for students and teachers. Through these platforms, teachers and students can perform their tasks quickly and efficiently.

However, no-code platforms also have disadvantages. It takes a long time for the instructions and functions of the platforms to be understandable. It can also create limitations for students to properly analyze the learning process.

All short-come, no-code platforms have disadvantages despite being useful tools in the educational process. These platforms make it easier to learn, require good ways to get to work and master yourself, and help students get a quality job

Visual programming systems are considered relevant in education because they help facilitate learning for students and teachers. These systems are a good starting point in the study of programming, creating motivation for students interested in programming.

These systems allow the creation and attachment of complex programs for students and teachers. In doing so, the systems make it easier to create a program through graphical interfaces, and students and faculty can also choose a language that suits them. This makes it more convenient to learn programming.

Visual programming systems help students explore their interest in programming and their conceptual understanding of programming. These systems make it easier for them to create algorithms and shapes, and allow them to learn the techniques they use to create their own applications. Also, visual programming systems cover just as many aspects of creating a program on a computer for students, including the initial concepts of program creation, testing and detection of created programs, error finding and Correction, and other aspects.

Conclusion. Visual programming systems make it easier for students to learn programming and give them conceptual insight. These systems help create complex programs and are considered to be a good starting point for students when learning how to create a program on a computer.

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